

KWARA STATE UNIVERSITY, MALETE

The University for Community Development

Faculty of Arts

**A PSYCHO- PHONOLOGICAL ANALYSIS OF THE SPEECH PATTERNS
OF SELECTED INFANTS**

BY

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DEDICATION

This study is dedicated to the Almighty, God, who has been my source of Strength, Grace and Wisdom throughout my study-period. May His name be forever praised!

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ABSTRACT

The perception of sound is basic to language acquisition and it is an important aspect of psycholinguistics. The first level of language appraisal is phonology, which studies sounds of different languages. This study examined speech patterns of selected infants from a psycho-phonological perspective. Six (6) infants between the ages of one and two were interviewed at the domestic setting and twenty (20) utterances of these infants were examined using two theories of psycholinguistic and phonological orientations—Watson’s (1913) Behavioral Theory and Ladefoged and Johnson’s (2011) Cognitive Theory of Speech Perception. The data samples were analysed both perceptually and acoustically, using the Praat software. Using Praat software, acoustic analysis was used to determine the pitch, spectrogram, and duration of speech patterns. From the demographic, perceptual and acoustic analysis, it has been found that, infants within the studied age bracket often have difficulty processing information and producing speech, which leads to erroneous responses. Additionally, it has been found that that the behavioral outlook of the studied infants depicts insensitivity to the seriousness of communication context and this also have impact on their level of perception and responses. In conclusion, this psycho-phonological inquiry has given an insight into the understanding of how infants interact with and represent language.

CHAPTER ONE

GENERAL INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background to the Study

Phonology describes the way sounds function within a given language or across languages to encode meaning. Phonology is not only about phonemes and allophones. Phonology also concerns itself with the principles governing the phoneme systems—that is, with what sounds languages 'like' to have, which sets of sounds are most common (and why) and which are rare (and also why). It turns out that there are prototype-based explanations for why the phoneme system of the languages of the world have the sounds that they do, with physiological/acoustic/perceptual explanations for the preference for some sounds over others. (Nathan 2008)

According to *oxford Dictionary* (p. 675) phonology can be defined as the system of contrastive relationship among the speech sounds that constitute the fundamental components of a language.

From this definition, it could be inferred that phonology account for possible variations that emerge in speech production, most of which are context driven. Among the contexts which drive these variations include social and psychological contexts. It is based on this trajectory that this study sets out to examine a psycho-phonological analysis of the speech patterns of selected infants

1.2 Statement of the Problem

The infants' perception and production to speech will be analysis, infants' behavioral approach to the speech production will be completely different from the adult, in term of pronunciation, perception to an utterance, speech motion skill and their behavioral approach to an utterance. Also the exposure of the infants to the spoken English as made it imperative to investigate their

perception and production of speech. This is to investigate the speech patterns of an infants' spoken renditions.

1.3 Aim and Objectives of the Study

The aim of this study to embark on the study of a psycho-phonological analysis of the speech patterns of selected infants. Specifically, the objectives of this research are to:

- i. examine the speech perception of the selected infants aged six months to two years.
- ii. investigate the characteristics of an infant's behavioral approach toward speech perception ; and
- iii. evaluate the remarkable differences in the level of speech perception and production of the studied infants?

1.4 Research Questions

The following research questions are posed to give the study a focus.

- i. What are the speech perception of the selected infants aged six months to two years?
- ii. What characterise infants' behavioral approach toward speech perception?
- iii. Are there remarkable differences in the level of speech perception and production of the studied infants?

1.5 Justification of the Study

Several studies have been carried out on phonological analysis and different research has also been done on speech using different studies. Related studies conducted include: Basel et al. (2020), who embarked on a phonological analysis on identification of speaker. Gobir and Adwoa (2022), conducted a research on an interlanguage phonological approach to the analysis of selected

Ghanaian newscasters' rendition. Alabi and Gobir (2021), worked on an analysis of the phonological features of selected three year old pupils' speech. Similarly, Gobir (2021), adopted a clinical approach to the phonological assessment of selected three year old students' rendition. The current study is an additional to the already existing studies which seeks to fill the vacuum on research by examining psycho-phonological analysis of the speech patterns of selected infants.

1.6 Scope of the Study

The study focuses on a psycho-phonological analysis of the speech patterns of selected infants. Emphasis will be placed on the speech perception, production and behavior of a speakers in an utterance. This study will make use of Ladefoged and Johnson (2011) conceptual approach, "Cognitive Theory of Speech Perception" and "Behavioral Theory" by Watson (1913). Who says that only observable behavior should be studied, as cognition, emotions and mood are far too subjective, while cognitive theory of speech perception discusses the instrumental tools to archive the aim of acoustic speech analysis with supplemental physiological techniques for observing consonant place of articulation and a focus on discovering what speakers of a language do with their mouth, vocal folds and lungs in other to pronounce their language at segmental phonetic level.

1.7 Research Methodology

This research focus is on selected infants and the method which will be adopted for this research is both qualitative and quantitative approach because emphasis will be made on the explanatory and little towards to quantitative aspect. This work is based on the following

- i. The speakers to be selected are infants which they are the range of six month to two years of age.

- ii. Six (6) speakers will be selected for the analysis.
- iii. Selected interviews of infants will also be examined.
- iv. Spectrogram and praat representations will be used for the analysis of the selected infants.

1.8 Summary

This chapter provides a details background to the current study. It includes an introductory background to the study, the statement of the problem, the aim and the objectives of the study, the research question, the justification of the study, the scope of the study, and the research methodology.

CHAPTER TWO

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Introduction

This chapter contains a review of previous works on the subject of this research, which is phonology. This chapter entails the theoretical framework for the study will also constitute the discussion in this chapter.

2.2 Phonology

Phonology is one of the core fields that compose the discipline of linguistics, which is defined as the scientific study of language structure. Phonology is the study of sound in the context languages (Poole, 1995). Phonology deals with sound structure in individual Language: The way distinction in second structure of the 'same' element varies as a function of the other sounds in its context (Anderson 2001, pg 11386). According to Odden (2005), phonology is one of the core fields that compose the discipline of linguistics. Phonology is typically defined as the study of speech sounds of a language or languages and the law governing them, particularly the law governing the composition and combination of speech sounds in language. This definition does not reflect a segmental bias in the historical development of the field and we can offer a more general knowledge: the study of the knowledge and representations of sound system of human languages. From a neurobiological or cognitive neuroscience perspective, one can therefore consider phonology as the study of the mental model for human speech (George H, Steven L. Small 2016, pg 141-151). In this brief review, we restrict ourselves to spoken language, although analogous concerns hold for signed language (Brentari, 2011). Clark and Yallop (1995), also cited phonology is concerned with speech with the ways in which human produce and hear speech. Ladefoged

(1982, p.23) also describe phonology as the system and pattern of sounds that occurs in a language. He said that it involves studying a language to determine its distinctive sound and to find out which sound which sound conveys a different in meaning. It can be concluded that phonology is the study of the sound of a language. Phonology serves as lubrication for communication because it organizes human sounds and speech (Omachonu, 2010). Homby (2010) explains that phonology is the study of speech sound of a particular language. Phonology provides a better understanding of the correlation between the motor corex, cranial nerves, and the articulator organ. The motor cortex is the control center for speech. It is important to discuss about speech production in which it incorporate some aspects in which it will also be introduce in this research.

Speech Production

Speech production is the process of uttering articulated sounds or words, i.e., how humans generate meaningful speech. It is a complex feedback process in which hearing, perception, and information processing in the nervous system and the brain are also involved (Stan Z. Li, Anil K. Jain 2015, and Pg.1493). Speech production is the process by which thoughts are translated into speech. This includes the selection of words, the organization of relevant grammatical forms, and then the articulation of the resulting sounds by the motor system using the vocal apparatus. Ladefoged and Johnson (2011, p.2) also explained speech production as the result of the tongue and lips. He explains that the tongue and lips movement as gestures forming particular sound. It is possible to convey information by gestures of our hands that people can see, but in making speech that people can hear, humans have found marvelously efficient way to give information. The gestures of the tongue and lips are made audible so that they can be heard and recognized.

Ladefoged and Johnson (2011, p.2) also said that making speech gesture audible involves pushing air out of the lung while producing a noise in the throat or mouth. These basic noises are changed by the actions of the tongue and lips. So, it means that each sound is different because of the different of the tongues and lips' action. Producing any energy. In nearly all speech sounds, the basic source of power is the respiratory system pushing air out of the lungs. It can be concluded, that is possible to produce sound or speak any language when we are breathing in. They also cited in (p.5) that the speech mechanism as a whole shows the four main component which are the airstream process, the phonation process, the oro-nasal process, and the articulatory process. The airstream process includes all the ways of pushing air out that provide the power for speech. We have considered just the respiratory system, the lungs pushing the prime mover in this process, while the phonation process is the name given to the actions of the vocal folds. Only the two possibilities have been mentioned: voiced sounds in which the vocal folds are vibrating voiceless sounds in which they are apart. The possibility of the airstream going out through the mouth, as in (v) or (z), or the nose, as in (m) and (n), is determined by the oro-nasal process. The movement of the tongue and lips interacting with the roof of the mouth and the pharynx are part of the articulatory process. In speech production, when the two folds close in order to vibrate, they generate periodic tones that lead to the sonorant sounds that form the voiced sounds such as the vowels, the laterals, the nasals and all other voiced consonants. But when the two vocal folds open and are not vibrating, the air from the lungs passes through them freely into the vocal tract. The tones generated in this process are referred to as aperiodic, and they form the obstruent sounds that generate the voiceless consonants.

Figure 1: The Four Main Components of the Speech Mechanism

Source: Ladefoged & Johnson (2011, p.7)

Finally, the articulatory process is the most obvious one: it take place in the mouth and it is the process through which we can differentiate most speech sounds. In the mouth we can distinguish between the oral cavity, which acts as a resonator, and the articulators, which can be active or passive. So, speech sounds are distinguished from one another in terms of the place and manner how they are articulated.

2.2.1 The Sound System of English

The two English systems are vowels and consonant sounds. These two categories are discussed in the sub subsections.

a) Vowel Sounds

The word vowel comes from the Latin word *vocalis*, meaning “vocal” (i.e. relating to the voice). . In English, the word vowel is commonly used to refer both to vowel sounds and to the written symbols that represent them (a, e, i, o, u and sometimes y). According to Clark and Yallop (1990. P.3). vowel refers to sound, not to letter. From there ideology vowel talk about vowel sound not vowel letter. There is much kind of English vowel sounds. They are short vowel, long vowel and diphthong (Bakar, 2006). It also was in accordance with Roach (2009).

Figure 2: Vowel Chart

Source: Ladefoged & Johnson (2011, p. 46)

Short vowel means that we make short sounds. The symbol for these short vowel /i/ as in 'list', 'bit', 'pin', 'fish', etc. /e/ as in 'less', 'bet', 'men', 'yes', etc. /æ/ as in 'lass', 'bat', 'man', 'gas', etc. /ʌ/ as in 'cup', 'cut', 'come', 'rush', etc. /ɒ/ as in 'lost', 'pot', 'gone', 'cross', etc. and /u/ as in 'look', 'put', 'pull', 'push', etc.

Long vowels are the vowels which tend to be longer than the short vowels in similar context (Roach, 2009). The symbol for this long vowels are /i:/ as in 'least', 'beat', 'mean', 'peace', etc. /ɜ:/ as in 'learn', 'bird', 'fern', 'purse', etc. /a:/ as in 'last', 'card', 'half', 'pass', etc. /ɔ:/ as in 'lord', 'board', 'torn', 'horse', etc. and /u:/ as in 'Luke', 'food', 'soon', 'loose', etc.

Diphthong is also known as gliding vowel, is a combination of two adjacent vowels sounds within the same syllable. The symbol for this diphthong are. /ɪə/ as in "dear", "here", "near", "hear", "gear" etc. /eɪ/ as in "day", "take", "cake", "case", etc. . /eə/ as in "care", "there", "where", etc. . /ʊə/ as in "Sure", "tour", "cure", etc. /oʊ/ as in "throw", "grow", "soul", /ɔɪ/ as in "toy" "boy", "boil", "joy", "empty", "noise", etc. /aɪ/ as in "tie", "white", "mind", "time", "find", "right", etc. /aʊ/ as in "ground", "town", "snow", "hound", etc.

English has a larger number of vowel sounds, and this vowel can be differentiated by the term of the position of the highest point of the tongue and the position of the lips. Ladefogeb (2001, p. 12) cited that there are three major gesture that affect vowel sound. They are the height of the body tongue, the front and the back position of the tongue, and the degree of the lip rounding. Johnson (2011, p. 211) named it as main aspects of vowel quality. It is also important to know the production of vowel sounds to know the gesture of vowel

In the articulation of vowel sounds, it is identified that the passage of airstream of vowel sounds is relatively unobstructed. And this is differentiated by their gestures (articulation). They are the height of the body tongue, the front and the back position of the tongue, and the degree of the lip rounding. Johnson (2011, p. 19) also pointed that vowel sound in heed, hide, head, had, father, good, food gesture, the tongue tip is down behind the lower front teeth, and also the body of the tongue is domed upward. The highest point of the tongue is in the front of the mouth, in the first four vowel. Accordingly, these vowels are called front vowels. The tongue is fairly close to the roof of the mouth for the vowel in “heed”, slightly less close for the vowel in “hid”, and the lower still for the vowels in “head” and “had”. The vowel in heed is classified as a high front vowel, while the vowel in had as a low front vowel. The height of the tongue for the vowels in the other words is between these two extremes, and they are known as mid-front vowels. The vowel in hid is a mid-high vowel, and the vowel in head is a mid- low vowel.

From the above explanation, it can be conclude that /i/, /e/, /ae/, and /a/ are front vowels. /i/, is high close front vowel, /e/ is close mid-high vowel, while /ae/ open-mid vowel.

Figure 3: The Tongue Shape of the Front Vowel

This also explained that the tongue position of vowel sounds in father, good, food is close to the back surface of the vocal tract. They are classified as back vowels. The body of the tongue is highest in the vowel in food and lowest in the first vowel in father. The vowel in good is a mid-high back vowel. It can be concluded, from the explanation above that /u:/ is called a high back vowel, /a:/ is called a low back vowel, and /u/ is mid-high back vowel.

It is also known that lip gesture also has an effect in different vowels. According to Johnson (2011, p. 20) there is a movement of the lips in addition to the movement that occurs because of the lowering and rising of the jaw. This movement is called lip rounding. It is usually most noticeable in the inward movement of the corners of the lips. Vowels may be described as being rounded (as in who'd) or unrounded (as in heed).

The quality of a vowel depends on its overtone structure (Ladefoged 2011, p. 187). Vowel sound contains a number of different pitches simultaneously. There is the pitch at which it is actually

spoken, and there are different overtone pitches that give it distinctive quality. Vowel can distinguish by the differences in these overtones. The overtones are called formants. The quality of vowel usually based on the frequencies of the vowel, there is a relationship between articulatory of the vowels and the frequencies of those vowel.

Figure 4: The Articulator

From the linguist's perspective. Lindblom and Sundberg's work as cited on Clark and Yallop (1995, p.266), explain the general relationships between acoustic and articulatory factors:

- i. Jaw opening cause F1 to rise quite markedly, usually in the context controlling vowel height. It will cause F2 to rise if the tongue is retracted up towards the soft palate: this effect is strongest when the lips are spread, but minimal in other articulatory position. F3 may rise sharply at moderate jaw apertures when the tongue is raise towards the palate region.

- ii. Tongue body movement in a general anterior to posterior direction causes a modest rise in F1 if the jaw is kept at affixed opening (but the jaw is not normally kept in one position). Movement from anterior to neutral position results in large drop in F2 in all cases. From neutral to posterior position, F2 will tend to rise with small jaw opening, but continue to fall with larger jaw openings.
- iii. Tongue body shape, which controls the degree of tract constriction (assuming a constant jaw position), has little effect on F1 except that it results in a modest fall at maximum constriction if the tongue body is well forward. It has a strong effect on F2, causing it to fall substantially as constriction increases if the tongue body is in neutral or posterior position. An anterior tongue body position combined with maximum constriction results in a shape rise in F2. F3 is little effected by tongue body shape except for a modest fall at neutral and maximum constriction with an anterior tongue position.
- iv. Lip rounding has the general effect of lowering all the formant frequency, with the strongest effects observable on F2 and F3. The extent of the effect depends on what the tongue and jaw are doing at the same time.
- v. Lowering of the larynx makes the vocal tract longer and tends to lower all formant frequency: the degree of lowering of each formant partly depends on the overall state of the vocal tracts, in general, larynx height influences F2 and F4 more than F3.

Ladefoged also said that there are two features of vowel quality. They are height and backness that are used to contrast one vowel with another in nearly every language, and there are other features that are used less frequently. Ladefoged concluded that formant frequency have some

effect. Such as frequency of formant one affect height, frequency of two affect Backness, Frequency of formant three affect Rhotacization.

b) Consonant Sound

Consonant are all non-vowel sounds. According to Roach (2009, pg.10), a consonant is a speech sound that is articulated with complete or partial closure of the vocal tract. Consonants are classified along three dimensions: voicing, place of articulation, and manner of articulation.

2.2.2 The English Prosody

a) Syllable

Syllables also are the units that bear stress and serve as the “anchor points” for tones in tonal systems and in intonation. Hayes (2009, pg. 250). According to Ladefoged and Johnson (2011, Pg.258) a syllable is the smallest possible unit of speech. Every utterance must contain at least one syllable. It is convenient to talk of speech as being composed of segments such as vowels and consonants, but these segments can be observed only as aspects of syllables. A syllable can also be divided for descriptive purposes into its onset and rhyme. The rhyming part of a syllable consists of the vowel and any consonants that come after it—a fairly familiar notion. Any consonants before the rhyme form the onset of the syllable. The rhyme of a syllable can be further divided into the nucleus, which is the vocalic part, and the coda, which consists of any final consonants. Words such as I and owe consist of a single syllable that has only a rhyme, which is also the nucleus. They have neither an onset nor a coda. Words such as splint and stripes are single syllables containing onsets with three consonants and codas with two consonants. Sometimes, it is difficult to say whether a consonant is the coda of one syllable or the onset of another.

b) Stress

Stress can always be defined in terms of something a speaker does in one part of an utterance relative to another According to Ladefoged and Johnson (2011). Stress is generally taken to involve the force or intensity with which a syllable is uttered. Stress is also detectable from the many effects it has on segments, since it appears so often in the environment of segmental rules Hayes (2009). Stress is most easily identified in citation forms. In conversational speech, words can be unemphasized, and when this happens, some of the properties of stressed syllables may not be realized. In citation forms, a stressed syllable is usually produced by pushing more air out of the lungs in one syllable relative to others. A stressed syllable thus has greater respiratory energy than neighboring unstressed syllables. It may also have an increase in laryngeal activity. A stressed syllable is often, but not always, louder than an unstressed syllable. In declarative utterances it is usually, but not always, on a higher pitch. The most reliable thing for a listener to detect is that a stressed syllable frequently has a longer vowel than it would have if it were unstressed. But this does not mean that all long vowels are necessarily stressed. The second and third vowels in radio, for example, are comparatively long, but they do not have the extra push of air from the lungs that occurs on the first vowel. Conversely, the vowels in the first syllables of cupcake and hit man are comparatively short, but they have extra respiratory energy and so are felt to be stressed. Stress can always be correlated with something a speaker does rather than with some particular acoustic attribute of the sounds. When as listeners we perceive the stresses that other people are making, we are probably putting together all the cues available in a particular utterance in order to deduce the motor activity (principally the respiratory gestures) we would use to produce those same

stresses. It seems as if listeners sometimes perceive an utterance by reference to their own motor activities. When we listen to speech, we may be considering, in some way, what we would have to do in order to make similar sounds. Stress has several different functions in English. In the first place, it can be used in sentences to give special emphasis to a word or to contrast one word with another. As we have seen, even a word such as *and* can be given a contrastive stress. The contrast can be implicit rather than explicit.

c) Tone and Intonation

In a tone language, pitch is used to distinguish words, and must appear in the lexical entries of morphemes, just like phonemic segmental information. As with segmental phonemes, one can often find minimal pairs and other sets for tone (Hayes 2009, pg. 291). Pitch variations that affect the meaning of a word are called tones. In the majority of the languages in the world, the meaning of a word depends on its tone. All languages also use intonation, the use of pitch variations, to convey syntactic information. (Lafeoged and Johnson 2011). The simplest kind of tone language is that in which there are only two possible tones, high and low. Tones may be transcribed in many ways. One of the simplest systems is to mark a steady (or level) high pitch by an acute accent over the vowel [á] and a level low pitch by a grave accent [à]. Middle pitches can be left unmarked. Occasionally, tones occur on consonants that are not normally syllabic. Tone languages also use intonational pitch changes. In many tone languages, ordinary statements will have a generally falling intonation, and at least some questions will have a rising intonation over part of the utterance. Doubt, anger, excitement, and many other emotional signals will be conveyed by intonations similar to those in English, the distinctive tones of individual words being

superimposed on the overall patterns. As in English, the regular intonation of a sentence often marks syntactic boundaries. In most languages, there is a downward trend of the pitch over a syntactic unit such as a sentence. This general pitch lowering is known as declination. However, the specific phonetic realization of declination varies from language to language. Variations in pitch are used in a number of different ways. In the first place, they convey nonlinguistic information about the speaker's emotional state and, to some extent, personal physiological characteristics. Second, in all languages, differences in pitch convey one or more kinds of linguistic information. The linguistic uses of pitch are intonation (the distinctive pitches in a phrase), which in all languages conveys information about the syntactic components of the utterance, and tone (the distinctive pitches within a word), which may convey both lexical information about the meaning of the word and the grammatical function of the word. Within tone languages, the tones can be divided into contour tones, which require the specification of a change in pitch within the syllable, and target tones, in which only a single target height needs to be specified for each syllable, the pitch changes within a syllable being regarded as simply the result of putting syllables together to form a sentence.

2.2.3 The Aspects of Phonetics

a) Place of Articulation

Places of articulation, proceeding from front to back which indicate the approximate path taken by an articulator in making contact with the opposite wall of the vocal tract.

- Bilabial sounds are made by touching the upper and lower lips together. English has a voiceless bilabial stop [p], a voiced bilabial stop [b], and a (voiced) bilabial nasal [m]. Note that the

description just given follows the standard form for describing a consonant: voicing, then place, then manner. In the case of nasals and approximants, which are normally voiced, it is common to specify only place and manner.

- Labiodental sounds are made by touching the lower lip to the upper teeth. English has a voiceless labiodental fricative [f] and a voiced one, [v].

- Dental sounds are made by touching the tongue to the upper teeth. This can be done in a number of ways. If the tongue is stuck out beyond the teeth, the sound is called an interdental, though we will not be concerned with so fine a distinction. English has a voiceless dental fricative [θ] (thin) and a voiced one [ð] (the).

- Alveolar sounds are made by touching the tip or blade of the tongue to a location just forward of the alveolar ridge. English has a voiceless alveolar stop [t], a voiced alveolar stop [d], voiceless and voiced alveolar fricatives [s] and [z] (both of them sibilants), a voiced alveolar nasal [n], a voiced alveolar lateral approximant [l],⁵ and a voiced alveolar central approximant [ɹ].

Figure 5: Place of Articulation

Source: Hayes (2009, p. 9)

- Palato-alveolar sounds (sometimes called post-alveolar) are made by touching the blade of the tongue to a location just behind the alveolar ridge. English has a voiceless palato-alveolar fricative [ʃ] (shoe), a voiced palato-alveolar fricative [ʒ] (vision), a voiceless palato-alveolar affricate [tʃ] (church), and a voiced palato-alveolar affricate [dʒ] (judge).
- Retroflex sounds are made by curling the tongue tip backward, and touching the area just behind the alveolar ridge. Some English speakers lack the alveolar approximant [ɹ] and instead have a retroflex one, transcribed [ɻ]; retroflex stops and affricates are common in languages of India and Australia. In the strict sense of the term, palato-alveolars and retroflexes have the same place of

articulation: the same place on the roof of the mouth is contacted. They differ in the part of the tongue (blade or tip) that makes the contact. Conventionally, however, palato-alveolar and retroflex are referred to as separate places of articulation.

- Palatal sounds are made by touching the tongue blade and the forward part of the tongue body to the hard palate. [j] (young) is sometimes described as a palatal approximant; various languages have a variety of other manners of articulation at the palatal place.

- Velar sounds are made by touching the body of the tongue to the hard or soft palate. English has three velar sounds: a voiceless velar stop [k], a voiced velar stop [g], and a velar nasal [ŋ] (sing).

- Uvular sounds are made by moving the tongue body straight back to touch the uvula and neighboring portions of the soft palate. The “r” sound of French and German is usually a voiced uvular fricative, [ʁ]. The nasal consonant that occurs at the end of many words in Japanese, transcribed here with [ŋ], is pronounced by many speakers as uvular [ɴ].

- Pharyngeal sounds are made by moving the tongue body down and back into the pharynx. A voiceless pharyngeal fricative is transcribed [ħ]; it occurs for example in Arabic.

- Glottal sounds are made by moving the vocal cords close to one another. English has a voiceless glottal fricative [h].

		Place of articulation							
		bilabial	labio-dental	dental	alveolar	palato-alveolar	palatal	velar	glottal
Manner of articulation	nasal (stop)	m			n			ŋ	
	stop	p b			t d			k g	ʔ
	fricative		f v	θ ð	s z	ʃ ʒ			h
	(central) approximant	(w)			ɹ		j	w	
	lateral (approximant)				l				

Figure 6: Consonant Chart

Source: Ladefoged & Johnson (2011, p. 46)

b) Manner

According to Hayes (2009), there are various manners of articulation. In a stop, the airflow through the mouth is momentarily closed off. This can be done by the two lips, forming [p] or [b]; by the tongue tip touching the alveolar ridge, forming [t] or [d]; by the tongue body touching the palate, forming [k] or [g]; and in other ways. In a fricative, a tight constriction is made, so that air passing through the constriction flows turbulently, making a hissing noise. Some of the fricatives of English are [f], [v], [θ] (the first sound of thin), and [ð] (the first sound of the). In sibilant fricatives, the mechanism of production is more complex: a stream of air is directed at the upper teeth, creating noisy turbulent flow. The four sibilant fricatives of English are [s], [z], [ʃ] (the first sound

of shin), and [ɛ] (the consonant spelled s in pleasure). An affricate is a stop followed by a fricative, made at the same location in the mouth in rapid succession so that the result has the typical duration of a single speech sound. English has two affricates: voiceless [tʃ] (as in church) and voiced [dʒ] (as in judge). As can be seen, the IPA symbol for an affricate is made with the symbols for the appropriate stop and fricative, optionally joined with a ligature. Affricates are often considered to be a species of stop; that is, “affricated stops.” In a nasal consonant, the velum is lowered, allowing air to escape through the nose. Most nasal consonants have a complete blockage within the mouth at the same time. The places of articulation for nasals are mostly the same as those for stops. The nasal consonants of English are [m] (mime), [n] (none), and [ŋ] (young). Nasals like [m, n, ŋ] in a certain sense are also stops, since they involve complete closure in the mouth; hence the term “stop” is ambiguous.

c) Voicing

In a voiced consonant, the vocal cords vibrate. For example, the “s” sound, for which the IPA symbol is simply [s], is voiceless, whereas the “z” sound (IPA [z]) is voiced. If you say “sa, za” while planting the palm of your hand firmly on the top of your head, you should feel the vibrations for [z] but not for [s]. The sounds [p t k] are voiceless. The sounds [b d g] as they occur in (for example) French or Japanese are voiced; in English they are often voiced for only part of their duration or even not at all; nevertheless the symbols [b d g] are traditionally used for them. (Hayes 2009:pg7)

2.3 Phonological Analysis

Phonological analysis is to establish distinctive difference between sounds, create the inventory of the phonemes and describe the phonemic system of a language. In other words, the aim of phonological analysis is the identification of the phonemes and their classification. To decide what phoneme it belongs to. There are two main approaches to phonological analysis. Formally distributional approach practiced by American structuralists is focused on the position of the sound in the word, or its distribution. Semantic method attaches special importance to meaning. It is widely used in this country. The analysis is performed through the system of phonological oppositions. It is based on the following fundamental phonological rule: phonemes can distinguish the meaning when opposed to one another in the same phonetic context (day - they, sheep - ship). So to establish the phonemic status of a sound it is necessary to oppose one sound to some other sound in the same phonetic context. This procedure is called commutation test. To conduct this test we must find the so-called minimal pairs. A minimal pair is a pair of words which differ in one sound only. So we replace one sound by another sound and try to find out if the opposed sounds belong to the same or different phonemes. Now, the commutation test may have three possible results: Pin - sin | the meaning is different so the opposed sounds belong to different phonemes. P(h)in - pin | the meaning is the same so the opposed sounds belong to the same phoneme. Pin - hin | we have a meaningless word, so we can't make any conclusion about the phonemic status of the second sound, we can't identify it. It should be noted that there are different types of oppositions. If the members of the opposition differ in one articulatory feature the opposition is called single. Pen - ben | [p] is fortis (voiceless), [b] is lenis (voiced). If there are two distinctive features, the opposition is double. Pen - den | [p] is labial, fortis, [b] is forelingual, lenis.

If three distinctive features are marked, the opposition is triple (multiple). Pen -then | the differentiating features: occlusive -constrictive, labial -interdental, fortis - lenis. To establish the system of phonemes of a language it is necessary to oppose sounds in all possible positions (initial, medial, final). But there are cases when the sounds can't be used in the same position and can't be opposed. For example [h] is never used in final position, [n] is never used in the initial position. These sounds are treated as different phonemes on the basis of native speakers' knowledge and their phonetic dissimilarity which illustrates that they cannot be allophone of one phoneme.

There is another case which is analyzed and explained by different schools of classical phonology. In some cases different sounds occur in the same position and in the same phonetic context, but the meaning of the word remains unchanged. They are called "free variants". Despite these difficulties the semantic method of phonological analysis is widely used and fulfills the task of systematizing the sounds of a language.

2.3.1 Phonemic Analysis

Phonemics analysis is the process of analysis a spoken language to figure out what is phoneme are, what the allophones are of those phonemes, and what each xylophone's distribution is. The resulting overall is called a phonemicization of the language. During the development of phoneme theory in the mid-20th century phonologists were concerned not only with the procedures and principles involved in producing a phonemic analysis of the sounds of a given language, but also with the reality or uniqueness of the phonemic solution. These were central concerns of phonology. Some writers took the position expressed by Kenneth Pike: "There is only one accurate phonemic analysis for a given set of data", while others believed that different analyses, equally valid, could

be made for the same data. Yuen Ren Chao (1934), in his article "The non-uniqueness of phonemic solutions of phonetic systems" stated "given the sounds of a language, there are usually more than one possible way of reducing them to a set of phonemes, and these different systems or solutions are not simply correct or incorrect, but may be regarded only as being good or bad for various purposes". The linguist F. W. Householder referred to this argument within linguistics as "God's Truth" (i.e. the stance that a given language has an intrinsic structure to be discovered) vs. "hocus-pocus" (i.e. the stance that any proposed, coherent structure is as good as any other). In the same period there was disagreement about the correct basis for a phonemic analysis. The structuralist position was that the analysis should be made purely on the basis of the sound elements and their distribution, with no reference to extraneous factors such as grammar, morphology or the intuitions of the native speaker; this position is strongly associated with Leonard Bloomfield.

2.3.2 Phonetic Analysis

Phonetic analysis refers to the ability to recognize sound or symbol relationships in order to identify a word. This involves a knowledge of the phonological patterns of the language, knowledge of the letters and their corresponding sounds in the particular word environment, the ability to identify such sound symbol relationships while doing "real" reading and the application of generalizations in situations calling for them. With the use of phonetic analysis, the user is able to blend the individual sounds in the given order to identify a word not recognized instantly as a sight word. Along with the other identification strategies, it is a necessary means to the end of identifying unknown words, because of the nature of the English language and its orthography. Phonetics is primarily an experimental science, which studies speech sounds from three viewpoints:

- Production: how sounds are made in the human vocal tract
- Acoustics: the study of the waveforms by which speech is transmitted through the atmosphere
- Perception: how the incoming acoustic signal is processed to detect the sound sequence originally intended by the speaker.

2.3.3 Acoustic Analysis

Acoustic analysis is the measurement of sound wave caused by component contacts inside equipment. Any sound, non-human or human, non-speech or speech, travels through a medium such as the air or water or metal. A sound is usually propagated or transmitted by wave, which is defined as the periodic displacement of pressure from one point to the other. Through these periodic movements, the wave is able to transmit or propagate a sound from one fixed place to the other. But specifically, human speech is transmitted by the sound waves that originate from the lungs into the larynx or what is called the voice box. The larynx is usually referred to as the voice box, mainly, because it houses the vocal folds whose precursor is the generation of the vibrations that give phonation or the sound waves that lead to the voiced sounds. The Source-Filter Theory recounts that the speech sound generation starts from the lungs, which pump air into the larynx. The air, so pumped, forces the vocal folds housed by the larynx to open and close. When the sound waves that escape through the folds get to the vocal tract, they are moderated by the various speech organs in the vocal tract by the process of filtration and the vocal tract acting as the acoustic filter. The filtering process converts the sound vibrations from the larynx into the individual speech sounds that we hear.

2.4 Phonological Theories

Phonological theories have arisen out of linguistics. Linguists are attempting to understand how language is organized in the brain. Up to the 1950s, the focus had been on analysis of what the speaker produced (surface form). There are two major critical reviews of phonological theories: linear phonological theory and the nonlinear phonological theory.

2.4.1 Linear Phonological Theories

Linear phonology assumes that speech is produced in a sequential fashion and that all distinctive features and sounds are equal. The linguistic theory that speech segments (phonemes) are arranged in sequential order and in that order convey a specific message; include natural phonology and distinctive features theories.

i. Natural Phonological Theory

Natural phonology is a theory based on the publications of its proponent David Stampe in 1969 and, more explicitly, in 1979. In this view, phonology is based on a set of universal phonological processes that interact with one another; those that are active and those that are suppressed is language-specific. Such simplifications are phonological processes that may affect an entire class of sounds sharing a common articulatory difficulty. Simplifications result in speech sound errors in the context of adult models, but those errors are unlearned because they stem from phonetic-physiological limitations. Learned speech sound errors cannot be attributed to a natural process (Donegan and Stampe, 1979). The theory is called natural because the children's simplifications of adult sound productions are due to their phonetic (speech production) limitations. Because children learning different languages simplify the adult production in similar ways, Stampe

proposed that phonological processes are both universal and natural. NPT retains the Chomskyan assumption (Chomsky, 1995) of innately given adult phonological system that children are supposed to possess. However, in contrast to the Chomskyan theorists, natural phonologists believe that children do not follow some kind of rules in learning to produce their speech sounds. Processes are not abstract cognitive or mental rules, but they are a product of phonetic or physiological limitations of young children trying to master speech sounds. Children's speech improves as their speech production mechanism becomes more competent and their productions better match the adult models. Consequently, the simplification processes fade.

ii. Distinctive Feature Theory

In 1968, Noam Chomsky and Morris Halle published *The Sound Pattern of English (SPE)*, the basis for generative phonology. In that view, phonological representations are sequences of segments made up of distinctive features. Distinctive feature theory is a classic and standard linear theory in which phonemic segments are a bundle of independent features that may combine with any other segment. Features are binary; all phonemes either have [+] or don't have [-]. Proponents of this theory believe that phonemes are stored in the brain as "bundles of features". Features are called "distinctive" because they allow us to distinguish among phonemes. They are based on acoustic properties (e.g., strident, voice). Articulatory properties (e.g., high, back, lateral, coronal). Function in syllable (e. g., consonantal, vocalic). Two phones are different phonemes if at least one of their features is different. /p/ = + consonantal, + anterior, - voice, and /b/ = + consonantal, + anterior, + voice.

2.4.2 Nonlinear Phonological theories

Nonlinear phonology emphasizes relationship among larger segments of language syllables, words, phrases as well as the impact of suprasegmental aspects of phonology- intonation, stress, and pause on speech production. This theory organizes segmental and supra segmental, properties of sound and speech into tiers that are interrelated hierarchically rather than linearly. Nonlinear phonology includes: optimality, auto segmental, metrical and feature geometry theory.

i. Auto segmental Phonology Theory

In 1976, John Goldsmith introduced auto segmental phonology. Auto segmental phonology theory is a nonlinear approach to phonology that allow phonological processes, such as tone and vowel harmony, to be independent of and extend beyond individual consonants and vowels. Goldsmith (1976) further says that these features are separate elements of the speech sound, which are often treated in phonology as part of the phonemes or segments of a speech. He argues that rather, these features should be treated as autonomous segments, thus, they have earned the name auto segmental features. Such segments are: length, quality, crescendo, tempo, rhythm, stress and intonation, the last three being most prominent in a language like English (Gimson, 1980: pp. 222-223; Jolayemi, 1999: pp. 79-89).

ii. Optimality Theory

Prince and Smolensky (1993) and McCarthy and Prince (1994) are the original proponents of optimality theory (OT). Optimality theory proposes that speech sounds may be marked (complex, more difficulty to produce, etc.) or unmarked (simple, easier to produce, etc.). Optimality replaces rules with markedness and faithfulness constraints. Constraints are common to all languages, but

their ranking are unique to each language. Speakers can violate constraints ranked lower, but not those ranked higher in their language. When speech is imminent, GEN the generator generates a variety of output (response) options and EVAL the evaluator selects an optimal output that is faithful to the higher-ranked constraints. There is no independent evidence for the existence of universal and innate constraints, specific language-based rankings, and the operation of GEN or EVAL. Assumptions of universality of phonological rules and even the existence of such rules are speculative. That children have innate phonological knowledge is an untenable assumption. OT it means sounds that are complex, difficult to produce, not natural, infrequent in languages, abnormal, unpredictable, later-acquired, language-specific, and perceptually weak. Being the opposite of marked, unmarked sounds are simple, easy to produce, natural, frequently occurring in languages, normal, predictable, early acquired, universal, and perceptually strong (Haspelmath, 2006; Hume, 2011).

iii. Metrical Phonology Theory

Metrical phonology is mostly concerned with the syllable structures, stress patterns, and rhythms of speech. It is a cover term which refers to several nonlinear theories of stress. The nonlinear theory of the representation of stress as introduced by Liberman (1975) and Liberman & Prince (1977) is a direct reaction to the linear analysis of stress proposed within the Sound Pattern framework developed by Chomsky & Halle (1968), in which stress is considered a property of individual segments (i.e. vowels). In metrical phonology, stress is seen as a relational property obtaining between constituents, expressed in metrical trees as a binary relation between sister

nodes which are labeled weak or strong. This theory of metrical phonology is further developed by e.g. Hayes (1980), Prince (1983), Kager (1989) and others.

iv. Feature Geometry Theory

Clement (1985) proponent's feature geometry is a phonological theory which represents distinctive features as a structured hierarchy rather than a matrix or a set. Feature geometry grew out of autosegmental phonology, which emphasizes the autonomous nature of distinctive features and the non-uniform relationships among them. It recognizes that some sets of features often pattern together in phonological and phonotactic generalizations while others rarely interact. Feature geometry comprises of nodes which are the laryngeal node and root node.

2.5 Conceptual Framework

The conceptual framework for the study is Ladefoged and Johnson (2011) *Cognitive Approach to Speech perception* refers to the suite of (neural, computational, cognitive) operations that transform auditory input signals into representations that can make contact with internally stored information: the words in a listener's mental lexicon. Speech is typically studied using single speech sounds (e. g., vowels or syllables), spoken words, or connected speech (D. Poeppel, 2015). G.W. McRoberts (2008) Speech perception refers to the ability to perceive linguistic structure in the acoustic speech signal. During the course of acquiring a native language infants must discover several levels of language structure in the speech signal, including phonemes (speech sounds) which are the smallest units of speech. Although phonemes have no meaning in themselves, they are the building blocks of higher-level, meaningful linguistic units or structures, including morphemes, words, phrases, and sentences. Each of the higher-level units are composed

of units at the next lower level using rules that are specific to each language (i.e., morphology, grammar, or syntax). Thus, sentences are made up of phrases, phrases are composed of words, and words are made up of morphemes. Each of the meaningful units are composed of one or more phonemes. In a very real sense, the ability to perceive differences between and categorize phonemes provides the underlying capacity for the discovery of the higher levels of language structure in the speech signal. Speech perception, the process by which we employ cognitive, motor, and sensory processes to hear and understand speech, is a product of innate preparation ("nature") and sensitivity to experience ("nurture") as demonstrated in infants' abilities to perceive speech. Studies of infants from birth have shown that they respond to speech signals in a special way, suggesting a strong innate component to language. Other research has shown the strong effect of environment on language acquisition by proving that the language an infant listens to during the first year of life enables the child to begin producing a distinct set of sounds (babbling) specific to the language spoken by its parents. Watson's (1913) Psychology approach to **Behavioral Theory** is a theory of learning based on the idea that all behaviors are acquired through conditioning, and conditioning occurs through interaction with the environment. Behaviorists believe that our actions are shaped by environmental stimuli Krapfl (2016). In simple terms, according to this school of thought, also known as behavioral psychology, behavior can be studied in a systematic and observable manner regardless of internal mental states Abramson (2013). Behavioral theory also says that only observable behavior should be studied, as cognition, emotions, and mood are far too subjective. Trict behaviorists believe that any person—regardless of genetic background, personality traits, and internal thoughts— can be trained to perform any task, within the limits of their physical capabilities. It only requires the right conditioning.

2.5.1 Approaches to the Speech Perception

i. Cognitive Process of Speech Perception

Cognition is the mental action or process of acquiring knowledge and understanding through thought, experience, and the senses. It encompasses all aspects of intellectual functions and processes such as: perception, attention, thought, imagination, intelligence, the formation of knowledge, memory and working memory, judgment and evaluation, reasoning and computation, problem-solving and decision making, comprehension and production of language. According to Indeed (2023) defined cognitive process of speech perception as a series of chemical and electrical signals that occur in the brain that allow you to comprehend your environment and gain knowledge. Neurons release chemicals that create electrical signals in nearby neurons, building a mass of signal that are then translated into conscious interpretation of the five senses, procedural knowledge and emotional reactions are all example of cognition. It is the process that involved acquiring information and the processing it to be accessed again in the future. Cognitive processing allows people to think, learn, and solve problem. (P. Mccaw & A.Diamond 2022). Ladefoged and Johnson (2011, p.293) cites that it is worth noting that the phonetic implementation view assumes that words are stored in memory in their most basic phonetic form, from which we calculate phonetic variation using phonetic implementation rules

Speech Motor Control

Speech motor control as the systems and strategies that regulate the production of speech, including the planning and preparation of movements (sometimes called motor programming) and the execution of movement's plans to result in muscle contractions and structural displacements

(R D Kent 2000). Ladefoged and Johnson (2011, p.289) cites that the number of free parameters (separate muscle activations) that must be controlled in speech has been called a degrees of freedom problem because a flat control structure in which the tension of each muscle is separately controlled presents a control problem of exceeding complexity. The solution to the degrees of freedom problem that has been achieved in the speech motor control system (and most other motor control systems, like swallowing, walking, reaching, looking, etc.), is to organize the control system hierarchically in goal-oriented coordinative structures.

- In Speech motor control, the combination of words in connected speech is paramount. According to Ladefoged and Johnson (2011, p.115) connected speech is useful method to begin examining the motions that make up the words of English (in fact, any language). However speech is not really made of a variety of distance gestures, and we don't typically speak in isolated words anyway. To be able to see the key characteristics of particular vowels and consonants. The citation form of a word is what it sounds like when you pronounce it by itself. One syllable is completely stressed, and the vowel quality is not diminished. However, there could be a lot of changes in connected speech. When words are said in connected speech, they may be pronounced with varying degrees of emphasis, and this results in varying degrees of deviation from the citation form (which can be taken as the most emphatic, phonetically full form of the word). The range of phonetic variability found in connected speech is a good deal greater and more subtle than the variability found in citation forms, and this makes it difficult to describe the sound patterns of conversational speech as alternations among phonetic symbols; quantitative measurement of duration,

amplitude, and frequency is often a more insightful way to proceed. Some useful observations about phonetic reduction in conversational speech can be based on careful phonetic transcription. The key difference between citation speech and connected speech is the variable degree of emphasis placed on words in connected speech. This “degree of emphasis” is probably related to the amount of information that a word conveys in a particular utterance in conversation. The citation speech/conversational speech difference is particularly noticeable for one class of words. Closed-class words such as determiners (a, an, the), conjunctions (and, or), and prepositions (of, in, with)—the grammatical words—are very rarely emphasized in connected speech, and thus their normal pronunciation in connected speech is quite different from their citation speech forms. As with other words, closed-class words show a strong form, which occurs when the word is emphasized, as in sentences such as “He wanted pie and ice cream, not pie or ice cream”. There is also a weak form, which occurs when the word is in an unstressed position.

ii. Sensory Process of Speech Perception

According to kidsense (2023) sensory process is also known as the effective registration (and accurate interpretation) of sensory input in the environment (including one’s body). It is the way the brain receives, organizes and responds to sensory input in order to behave in a meaningful and consistent manner. It is also defined as the organization of sensory information from the body and the external world that allows a person to interact effectively with their physical and social environments (Ayres, 2005). Sensory process involves the perception, registration, and interpretation of different sensory stimuli in the environment.

2.5.2 Approaches to Behavioral Theory

i. Methodological Behaviorism

Methodological behaviorism states that observable behavior should be studied scientifically and that mental states and cognitive processes don't add to the understanding of behavior. Methodological behaviorism aligns with Watson's ideologies and approach.

ii. Radical Behaviorism

Radical behaviorism is rooted in the theory that behavior can be understood by looking at one's past and present environment and the reinforcements within it, thereby influencing behavior either positively or negatively. This behavioral approach was created by the psychologist.

2.6 Summary

In this chapter, various discussion of relevant literature related to this study are presented. The chapter presents, it reviewed major concepts that are related to the topic, and the conceptual framework for the study was also reviewed.

CHAPTER THREE

DATA ANALYSIS

3.1 Introduction

This chapter contains the analysis of the selected data, for the study which are the speeches of infants between six months and two years. The data are analysed using Ladefoged and Johnson (2011), Cognitive Theories of Speech Perception and Behavioral Theory (1913). The samples are analysed with a focus on demography analysis, speech perceptual and acoustic analysis.

3.2 Data Presentation

The data for this study constitutes selected utterances of six Nigerian infants (6 months- 2 years), collected using the interview and participatory observation method. Below is the presentation of the dialogue between the researcher and the subjects. This is pertinent as it provides the basis for the analysis of the perceptual behavior of the research subjects. Subsequently, the superscript, which is the standard (model) realisation and the subscript, the speakers' manifestation (variants) are juxtaposed.

Conversation between the researcher and the infants

Conversation 1

How are you? - Fine

Are you sure, you are fine? –Yes

How are you? – how are you

How are you? – zeenat

Is that your name? – is it your name

What is your name? – what is your name, am fine

I can hear you – are you hear you

Mummy fork

This is it

See

Conversation 2

How are you? – fine

Conversation 3

How are you? - how are you

How are you? – fine, how are you

Conversation 4

What is your name? – Basit

How are you? – fine

Conversation 5

How are you? – fine

Are you sure, you are fine? –Yes

Conversation 6

What is your name? – Roshida

How are you? – how are you

How are you? - fine

Table 1: A Juxtaposition of the Superscript and the Subscript Realizations

DATA	SAMPLE	UTTERANCE (LEXICO- GRAMMATICAL STRUCTURE	SUPERSCRIPT (SBE)	SUPERSCRIPT (SBE)
1	i	Fine	/fain/	/vain/
	ii	Yes	/jɛs/	/ji:s/
	iii	How are you?	/haʊ a:rju:/	/a:wæ ju:/
	iv	Zeenat	/zi:nat/	/sɪnæt/
	v	Is that your name?	/ɪzðæt Joʊneɪm/	/ɪs ɪ jæ neɪm/
	vi	What is your name, am fine	/wɔ:tɪzjoʊneɪm, æmfain/	/wɔ ɪt jæ neɪm, ænvain/
	vii	I can hear you	/aɪkænhɪəju:/	/a:ju: hɪəju:/
	viii	Mummy fork	/mʌmi fɔ:k/	/mʌmi fɔ:/
	xi	This is it	/ðɪs ɪz ɪt/	/dɪs ɪs ɪt/
	x	See	/si:/	/s:/
2	i	Fine	/fain/	/vain/
3	i	How are you?	/haʊ a:rju:/	/aʊə a:ju:/
	ii	Fine, how are you?	/fain, haʊ a:r ju: /	/vain, aʊə ju: /
4	i	Basit	/basit/	/basit/
	ii	Fine	/fain/	/vain/
5	i	Fine	/fain/	/fain/

	ii	Yes	/jɛs/	/jɛs/
6	i	Roshida	/roshida/	/roshida/
	ii	How are you	/haʊ a:rju:/	/haʊ a:rju:/
	iii	Fine	/faɪn/	/vaɪn/

3.3 Data Analysis

In this section, the analysis of the data will be carried out under the headings of perceptual analysis using the behavioral theory and the cognitive theory of speech perception. Subsequently, the data will be analysed acoustically using the praat application software.

3.3.1 Perceptual Analysis

Datum One

The perception of speech is one of the most fascinating attributes of human behavior; both the auditory periphery and higher centers help define the parameters of sound perception. During the data collection process, the speaker's motor skills in recognizing the question word is identified with the question word and find to be correct. The question is, "are you sure you're fine?" Her answer is "yes". Her answer correlates with the question pose, but her production to this sentence is one of the inaccurate statements that she has made. /ji:s/ instead of /jɛs/. The speaker is unable to distinguishing between /f/ and /v/. In the course of data collection, the question asked to test the speaker's perception is *how are you?* Her response is fine /fam/. Speaker's is able to perceive the question ask by given the correct answer but her production to the question was incorrect, she said vain /vam/ instead of fine /fam/.

Also, in her imitation of the question, there is evidence of mispronunciation of the expression "ow are you" as a word words /a:wæju:/. She produce the word Zeenat /smæt/, although that is her name but the production to the question ask at that moment was wrong. Also, she process the question she is ask twice, "Is that your name?" However, her verbal perception of the question is incorrect because she responded with the precise question she is ask, and her production of the

inquiry was also incorrect by saying *is it your name?* /ɪzɪt juə neɪm/, the correct pronunciation is *that your name* - /ɪs ɪ jænem/.

Meanwhile, she considered the question, "What is your name? am fine" Her verbal perception of the query, however, was erroneous because she responded with the exact question she is ask, and her production of the inquiry was also incorrect because she said what is your name? am fine- /wɔt jæ neɪm, æn vaɪn /instead of pronouncing her name. She pronounce it wrongly. while the speaker's is repenting a sentence being said to her. Her verbal understanding of the question was incorrect because her motor competence entails precise movements of the body's muscles. By saying the sentence again "*I can hear you*". Her production is inappropriate by saying *are you hear you* /a:ɹju: hɪə(ɪ) ju:/ instead of /a: ju: hɪəju:/.

"Mummy fork? "The speaker's behavior during the data collection show her motor skills to production. Though she wasn't asked, her verbal understanding of the question was incorrect because her motor competence entails precise movements of the body's muscles. What she produce in the cause of the question is not correspond. She say "Mummy fork"/mʌmɪ fɔ:/. "This is it" the speaker's said. Even though she wasn't questioned, she misunderstood the question verbally due to her lack of motor competence, which calls for exact movements of the body's muscles. She respond, "This is it" a manner that did not relate to the inquiry. Her production to the statement is erroneous by saying /dɪsɪsɪt/ instead of /ðɪs ɪz ɪt/. Also she said "See", she verbally says what she perceive to be the right thing because of her motor competence. The way she answer the question was not in line with it; she simply said, "See" /s:/.

Datum Two

The speaker's is unable to distinguish between /f/ and /v/ when she is ask *how are you?* During data collection, and her response is fine /fain/, indicating that she is able to perceive the question and give the correct response, but her production of the question in the cause of production is incorrect /vain/.

Datum Three

The speaker's motor skills at the time of recognizing the question word is inconsistent with the question word and judge to be incorrect. The question is, "How are you?" His answer is "our are you?" Her answer is stylishly correspondent with the question ask, but his production to the sentence by her is one of the incorrect statement she made /aʊə a:ju:/ instead of /haʊ a::r jʊ/. The question is, "How are you?" His answer is, "fine, our are you?" Her answer is the same as the question, but her production to the statement is incorrect. vain, our are you? /vain aʊə a:rjʊ/.

Datum Four

Speech Perception is the processes by which humans are able to interpret and understand the sounds used in language. The address is what is your name? His generation to the sentence is part of the right articulations he create. Basit- /ba:sit/. He is unable to distinguish between /f/ and /v/. When he is ask *how are you.* To test his perceptions. His answer is fine /vain/. He is able to understand the question by giving the correct answer, but his production was also incorrect /vam/ instead of /fain/.

Datum Five

Respondents is able to perceive the question being ask from her. The address is how are you? Her generation to the sentence is part of the right articulations she create. And her reply is fine- /Fam/. As part of the data collection, she is ask are you sure, you are fine? To test her perceptions. Her answer is yes /jes/. Speaker's is able to understand the question by giving the correct answer.

Datum Six

In the information gathering process, the speaker's motor skills in distinguishing the words in question are taken into account as they are relevant to the content of the discussion. The address is, what's your name? Her generation to movement is one of the right articulations she creates by giving the right answer to the question ask. Roshida /roshida/. The question is, how are you? her answer also asks the same question. Her creation of this sentence is her one of the false statements she made /haɔɑ:rjɔ/. The address is: How are you? And her production to the question is part of correct statement she make by saying /fam/

3.3.2 Demographic and Acoustic Data Analysis

Datum One

Demographic Analysis

The speaker's is a two years old female, whose L1 is Yoruba, while English language is her official language. At the period of data collection, the subject is enrolled at the crèche. Aside the subject

exposure to English language through her enrolment at the crèche, she has an educated parent. Hence, the subject has been exposed to the second language from home.

Acoustic Data Analysis

Sample One

Figure 7: (A) Spectrographic and (B) Graphical Representations of /vam/ by Speaker 1

The spectrogram analysis above, the duration of realisation of the word *fine* which is realised as /vam/ by the speaker is 0.379252 seconds. The pitch in both the spectrogram and the graph corresponds, likewise the duration of rendition of the word. However, the intensity is realized as 51.51.

Sample Two

(A)

(B)

Figure 8: (A) Spectrographic and (B) Graphical Representations of /jɪ:s/ by Speaker 1

The spectrogram analysis above, the duration of realisation of the word *fine* which is realised as /jɪ:s/ by the speaker is 0.511338 seconds. The pitch in both the spectrogram and the graph corresponds, likewise the duration of rendition of the word. However, the intensity is realized as 47.25.

Sample Three

(A)

(B)

Figure 9: Spectrographic and Graphical Representations of /a:wæ ju:/ by Speaker 1

The spectrogram analysis above, the duration of realisation of the word *how are you* which is realised as /a:wæju:/ by the speaker is 0.527596 seconds. The pitch in both the spectrogram and the graph corresponds, likewise the duration of rendition of the word. However, the intensity is realized as 35.68.

Sample Four

(A)

(B)

Figure 10: (A) Spectrographic and (B) Graphical Representations of /smæt/ by Speaker 1

The spectrogram analysis above, the duration of realisation of the word *zeenat* which is realised as /smæt/ by the speaker is 0.659206 seconds. The pitch in both the spectrogram and the graph corresponds, likewise the duration of rendition of the word. However, the intensity is realized as 40.82.

Sample Five

(A)

(B)

Figure 11: (A) Spectrographic and (B) Graphical Representations of /ɪs ɪ jænəm/ by Speaker 1

The spectrogram analysis above, the duration of realisation of the word *is that your name?* Which is realised as /ɪs ɪ jænəm/ by the speaker is 0.803107 seconds. The pitch in both the spectrogram and the graph corresponds, likewise the duration of rendition of the word. However, the intensity is realized as 32.89.

Sample Six

(A)

(B)

Figure 12: (A) Spectrographic and (B) Graphical Representations of /wɒt jæ neɪm, æn vɑːm / by Speaker 1

The spectrogram analysis above, the duration of realisation of the word *what is your name?* which is realised as /wɒt jæ neɪm, æn vɑːm/ by the speaker is 1.972222 seconds. The pitch in both the spectrogram and the graph corresponds, likewise the duration of rendition of the word. However, the intensity is realized as 31.8.

Sample Seven

(A)

(B)

Figure 13: (A) Spectrographic and (B) Graphical Representations of /a: ju: hɪəju:/by Speaker 1

The spectrogram analysis above, the duration of realisation of the word *I can hear you* which is realised as /a: ju: hɪəju:/ by the speaker is 0.986939 seconds. The pitch in both the spectrogram and the graph corresponds, likewise the duration of rendition of the word. However, the intensity is realized as 61.87.

Sample Eight

(A)

(B)

Figure 14: (A) Spectrographic and (B) Graphical Representations of /mʌmi fɔ:/ by Speaker 1

The spectrogram analysis above, the duration of realisation of the word *mummy fork* which is realised as /a: ju: hɪəju:/ by the speaker is 2.331927 seconds. The pitch in both the spectrogram and the graph corresponds, likewise the duration of rendition of the word. However, the intensity is realized as 34.22.

Sample Nine

(A)

(B)

Figure 15: (A) Spectrographic and (B) Graphical Representations of /**dis is it**/ by Speaker 1

The spectrogram analysis above, the duration of realisation of the word *this is it* which is realised as /**dis is it** / by the speaker is 0.974989 seconds. The pitch in both the spectrogram and the graph corresponds, likewise the duration of rendition of the word. However, the intensity is realized as 47.90.

Sample Ten

(A)

(B)

Figure 16: (A) Spectrographic and (B) Graphical Representations of /s:/ by Speaker 1

The spectrogram analysis above, the duration of realisation of the word *see* which is realised as /s:/ by the speaker is 0.662018 seconds. The pitch in both the spectrogram and the graph corresponds, likewise the duration of rendition of the word. However, the intensity is realized as 0.662.

3.3.3 Demographic and Acoustic Data Analysis

Datum Two

Demographic Analysis

The speaker's is a one years and six months old female, whose L1 is Yoruba, while English language is her official language. At the period of data collection, the subject hasn't been enrolled

to the crèche. She has an uneducated parent. Hence, the subject has been exposed to the second language from home through her environment.

Acoustic Analysis

Sample One

Figure 17: (A) Spectrographic and (B) Graphical Representations of /vain/ by Speaker2

The spectrogram analysis above, the duration of realisation of the word *this is it* which is realised as /vain/ by the speaker is 0.448957 seconds. The pitch in both the spectrogram and the graph corresponds, likewise the duration of rendition of the word. However, the intensity is realized as 0.449.

3.3.4 Demographic and Acoustic Data Analysis

Datum Three

Demographic Analysis

The speaker's is a two years old female, whose L1 is Yoruba, while English language is her official language. At the period of data collection, the subject is enrolled at the crèche. Aside the subject exposure to English language through her enrolment at the crèche, she has an uneducated parent. Therefore, the subject has been exposed to the second language at school.

Acoustic Analysis

Sample One

Figure 18: (A) Spectrographic and (B) Graphical Representations of /aʊə a: ju:/ by Speaker 3

The spectrogram analysis above, the duration of realisation of the word *how are you?* which is realised as /aʊə a: ju:/ by the speaker is 0.842857 seconds. The pitch in both the spectrogram and the graph corresponds, likewise the duration of rendition of the word. However, the intensity is realized as 47.45.

Sample Two

Figure 19: (A) Spectrographic and (B) Graphical Representations of /van, aʊəju: / by Speaker 3

The spectrogram analysis above, the duration of realisation of the word *fine, how are you?* which is realised as /van, aʊəju:/ by the speaker is 1.416417 seconds. The pitch in both the spectrogram and the graph corresponds, likewise the duration of rendition of the word. However, the intensity is realized as 45.58.

3.3.5 Demographic Analysis and Acoustic Analysis of the Data

Datum Four

Demographic Analysis

The speaker's is a two years old male, whose L1 is Yoruba, while English language is his official language. At the period of data collection, the subject is enrolled at the crèche. Aside the subject

exposure to English language through his enrolment at the crèche, he has an uneducated parent. Therefore, the subject has only be exposed to the second language at school.

Acoustic Data Analysis

Sample One

Figure 20: (A) *Spectrographic* and (B) *Graphical Representations of /ba:sit/ by Speaker 4*

The spectrogram analysis above, the duration of realisation of the word *what is your name?* which is realised as /basit/ by the speaker is 0.741723 seconds. The pitch in both the spectrogram and the graph corresponds, likewise the duration of rendition of the word. However, the intensity is realized as 43.71.

Sample Two

(A)

(B)

Figure 21: (A) Spectrographic and (B) Graphical Representations of /Vam/ by Speaker 4

The spectrogram analysis above, the duration of realisation of the word *what is your name?* which is realised as /basit/ by the speaker is 0.985578 seconds. The pitch in both the spectrogram and the graph corresponds, likewise the duration of rendition of the word. However, the intensity is realized as 44.89.

3.3.6 Demographic Analysis and Acoustic Analysis of the Data

Datum Five

Demographic Analysis

The speaker's is a two years old female, whose L1 is Igbo, while English language is her official language. At the period of data collection, the subject is enrolled at the crèche. Aside the subject

exposure to English language through her enrolment at the crèche, she has an educated parent. Hence, the subject has been exposed to the second language from home.

Acoustic Data Analysis

Sample One

Figure 22: (A) Spectrographic and (B) Graphical Representations of /fam/ by Speaker 5

The spectrogram analysis above, the duration of realisation of the word *fine* which is realised as /fam/ by the speaker is 0.305488 seconds. The pitch in both the spectrogram and the graph corresponds, likewise the duration of rendition of the word. However, the intensity is realized as 44.56.

Sample Two

(A)

(B)

Figure 23: (A) Spectrographic and (B) Graphical Representations of /jɛs/ by Speaker 5

The spectrogram analysis above, the duration of realisation of the word *yes* which is realised as /jɛs / by the speaker is 0.476100 seconds. The pitch in both the spectrogram and the graph corresponds, likewise the duration of rendition of the word. However, the intensity is realized as 36.16.

3.3.7 Demographic Analysis and Acoustic Analysis of the Data

Datum six

Demographic Analysis

The speaker's is a two years old female, whose L1 is Yoruba, while English language is her official language. At the period of data collection, the subject is enrolled at the crèche. Aside the subject

exposure to English language through her enrolment at the crèche, she has an educated parent. Therefore, the subject has been exposed to the second language from home.

Acoustic Data Analysis

Sample One

Figure 24: (A) Spectrographic and (B) Graphical Representations of /roshida/ by Speaker 6

The spectrogram analysis above, the duration of realisation of the word *Roshida* which is realised as /roshida/ by the speaker is 1.477370 seconds. The pitch in both the spectrogram and the graph corresponds, likewise the duration of rendition of the word. However, the intensity is realized as 39.3.

Sample Two

(A)

(B)

Figure 25: (A) Spectrographic and (B) Graphical Representations of /hau a:rjʊ/ by Speaker 6

The spectrogram analysis above, the duration of realisation of the word *how are you* which is realised as /hau a:rjʊ/ by the speaker is 0.716621 seconds. The pitch in both the spectrogram and the graph corresponds, likewise the duration of rendition of the word. However, the intensity is realized as 50.26.

Sample Three

(A)

(B)

Figure 26: (A) Spectrographic and (B) Graphical Representations of /vaim/ by Speaker 6

The spectrogram analysis above, the duration of realisation of the word *fine* which is realised as /vaim / by the speaker is 0.778776 seconds. The pitch in both the spectrogram and the graph corresponds, likewise the duration of rendition of the word. However, the intensity is realized as 43.92.

CHAPTER FOUR

SUMMMARY, FINDINGS AND CONCLUSION

4.1 Summary

The study aim at examining a psycho- phonological analysis of the speech patterns of selected infants. This research work comprises four chapter. Chapter one which is the general introduction established the background to the study and introduces us to the meaning of phonology. It also contains the statement of the problem, research questions, aim and objectives of the study, justification of the study, scope and the research methodology.

Chapter two of the study is the review of related literature that discussed the views of different scholars and concepts which are related to the topic. In this regard, the researcher examined the concept of phonology, speech production, and the sound system of English, the English prosody, the aspects of phonetics, phonological analysis, and phonological theories. Also, the review examined the conceptual framework of the study.

The third chapter focuses on the presentation afterwards the analysis of the eighteen infants utterances through the conceptual framework of Ladefoged and Johnson (2011) Cognitive Approach to Speech perception and Behavioral Theory John B. Watson's (1913). The analysis of the selected data was done using the tools reviewed in chapter two. The researcher examine

Chapter four, which is the last chapter of the research, concludes the research. It is a summary of the contents of the previous chapters, it provides the findings, and the ends with a conclusion and a reference section containing all the works cited in the course of the study.

4.2 Findings

So far, the study has been able to provide answers to the questions in the preliminary chapter. The questions and answers to them are presented as follows:

What are the speech perception of the selected infants aged six months to two years?

Question 1

The speech perception of an infants will focus on the demographic analysis, perceptual analysis, and acoustic data analysis and behavioral attitude used in an utterance.

All the six datum show the communication process of the subject in term of demographic in the aspect of age, ethnic, gender and educational status of the subject and her level of exposure to the second language, in which is part of the speaker perception patterns of speech to the question which she is ask. Perception of the infant to the most questions being ask seem incorrect due to their behavioral approach to the question and the process of the question in their brain, motor skills and also sensory aspect of their answer seem off, by repeating the question more than twice, before given the answer. Acoustic contains the duration of realisation of the speech pattern render by the subject, by using the praat application software for the analysis of the word, which should the spectrogram and the praat object of the speech render by the subject.

The behavioral attitude serve as an additional to the speech perception of an infants. It gives more meaning to the speech in term of identities of the subject interaction with the environment, which reflect on their production to the answers were given.

What characterise infants' behavioral approach towards speech perception?

Question 2

The behavioral approach of speech production is characterised by gradually increasing sensitivities toward to specific properties of the native language, unquestionably set the ground for a smooth transition from prelexical communicative abilities to language comprehension and production using linguistically relevant units such as words and sentences. Exposure to the ambient language rapidly modifies early, innate sensitivities toward auditory and linguistic stimuli. Infants' perceptual capacities, together with powerful learning mechanisms that can be applied to the language heard in the environment, facilitates the building of a first level of representation of sound pattern of the native language.

Are there remarkable differences in the level of speech perception and production of the studied infants?

Question 3

Acoustic analysis study of the waveforms by which speech is transmitted through the atmosphere use of both spectrogram and praat object to show the duration of the realization of words rendered by the subject, and also the pitch and intensity of the rendition will also be drawn out by the praat application software and they all have their specific meaning to speech.

4.3 Conclusion

In conclusion, Phonology which is one of the core fields that compose the discipline of linguistics, which is defined as the scientific study of language structure. This is why this research has accounted for a psycho-phonological analysis of the speech patterns of selected infants. This study

unravel how Speech perception and production is linguistically represent in a praat application software and the infant's behavior towards an utterance.

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